

HOW TO IMPLEMENT SOCIAL MEDIA IN THE CLASSROOM

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Annotation

Internet is the great tool to communicate and collaborate with others and it is the quickest way of exchanging information all over the world. Today there is no almost any sphere including teaching where Internet is not used. Now people clearly know that it makes the lives as well as teaching and learning easier. This scientific thesis discusses the issue of the role and importance of using different web sites in teaching digital natives and it shows several ways for the implementation of social media in the classroom.

Key words: Internet, social media, digital natives, computer-mediated technology, collaboration, stakeholders, extended learning.

Today as we live in the Era that is characterized by the global usage of Internet, we cannot imagine our lives without being in worldwide web. Particularly, for the youth so called 'digital natives' who were born and have been grown up with the development of Internet, it is hard to believe that there exists another world where people could live without digital media. People, including students at different ages, parents and other members of the society all around the world nowadays are more connected than ever through social media sites, like Facebook, Instagram, and Telegram. Although this century is negatively associated with the addiction to social media, there are a plenty of benefits in them. However, research indicates that educators have been sluggish to use social media as a platform for educational technology in the classroom.

Social media refers to a collection of websites and programs that let people create and share content for social networking.

It extends beyond simply sharing vacation photos online. Through apparent communities and a global network, it is an interactive computer-mediated technology for the exchange of different ideas, information, career interests, and other forms of expression.

Over the years, it has solidified its credibility as a reliable information source. It serves as a platform for interaction between businesses and their customers.

Many people believe that social media will serve more as a distraction in the classroom than as an aid. When teachers are aware of how to use it, it has been discovered that this is incorrect. Many teachers are reluctant to include social media into the classroom because they struggle with two issues: how to do so while maintaining a focus on standards and how to make sure the pupils are ethical online users. But what is crystal clear that our students have changed radically. Today's students are no longer the people our educational system was designed to teach.

As it is stated above, social networking may benefit in the classroom in different ways. First of all, social media platforms are excellent for displaying student work, publicizing

special events and activities, and recognizing student achievements. Social media offers a visual platform that enables users to view and better comprehend what is occurring in the school. We could, for instance, post images of the classroom and group projects to show off the effort of our pupils. We are able to communicate ideas and images in this way so that the neighborhood may see what goes on within the school. We are allowing transparency between schools and families and establishing openings for the community to support educational processes.

Stakeholders are generally thrilled to be able to observe what is happening in the classrooms because, before social media, this was only possible if parents and the local community were asked to visit the school and interact with the staff and students. Parents adore learning about and seeing what their kids are doing at school. The local community enjoys learning about what the local kids are studying and how they may get involved in that learning.

No doubt that being able to communicate the good things happening in classrooms makes every teacher very happy. Additionally, students also feel successful knowing that everyone can benefit from the fantastic work they are doing in class. If you don't tell your tale, someone else will, it's a common adage. Social media is the ideal platform for schools to communicate their narratives.

Moreover, it can be used as an extended learning by teachers: to supplement the curriculum's required reading assignments, teachers might use social media to share blog entries or articles with their students. Under the leadership of an experienced instructor, experiential learning is the greatest approach for students to comprehend the best practices of using social media responsibly. Social media usage enables educational institutions to "go green." This entails using less paper for parents to reply to the provided information as well as less paper for printing out notifications for school events. Social media platforms make it possible for information to reach all interested parties at once and for them to reply as required.

Social networking is an invaluable tool for making connections. In other words, social media plays the role of bridge between school and the society. Social media is a priceless tool for connecting parents, instructors, and students outside of the confines of the traditional classroom and school. Traditionally teachers get used to exchanging some newsletters with the parents. Students frequently have to bring home a newsletter that contains information about events at school and requests for parental action. The newsletter occasionally does not arrive at home that day or is even lost entirely. This process can be completed more quickly and effectively by using social media to spread this information and solicit the required responses.

Before using social media in the classroom, it is so vital for teachers to be extremely clear about their aims. Some teachers do this because it is the fad thing, but the purpose is important. The most important query should be, "Why to use?". Each teacher should think over what motivates their desire to incorporate social media into their classroom? Beyond the why, how will can it be put it to use? Is it to distribute assets? to run a chat? to establish links between students and one another?

Teacher must be clear about the actions, criteria, and information that will be connected to their social media activities.

Teachers also want to keep themselves and their pupils safe online. Although many social media platforms have built-in security measures, monitoring is the key to effective social media use in the classroom. Monitoring the content uploaded by students and other users and conducting class talks about digital citizenship are essential whether a teacher utilizes social media to give homework or stimulate group conversations. Using social media for collaboration and communication has several advantages. What more effective strategy to link the public to the schools given that the majority of people currently use social media? Crucial information should be shared with all stakeholders, and it is equally crucial to do so through a media that can reach the majority of those stakeholders. In order to better assist the public in accessing critical information, teachers are continuously looking for channels and platforms that are regularly used by communities and families.

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